

Università degli studi del Piemonte Orientale

“Amedeo Avogadro”

Department of Health Sciences

PhD Program in Food, Health and Longevity

XXXVII cycle

Double-Edge Sword of Ketogenic Diet: Hepatic Improvement at the Expense of Musculoskeletal Health

SSD MED/49

Ph.D coordinator:
Prof. Antonia Follenzi

Ph.D supervisor:
Prof. Flavia Prodam

PhD candidate:
Alessandro Antonioli

Academic years: 2021-2025

Share of adults who are overweight or obese, 1991

"Overweight" is defined here as a body mass index (BMI) above 25. BMI is a person's weight in kilograms divided by their height in meters squared.

Table Map Chart

Zoom to... 2D 3D

1991 1990 2022

Data source: World Health Organization - Global Health Observatory (2025) - [Learn more about this data](#)

Note: To allow for comparisons between countries and over time, this metric is age-standardized.

OurWorldinData.org/obesity | CC BY

In 2022 WHO considered overweight or with obesity 2.5 billion of adults.

Obesity pandemic: causes, consequences, and solutions—but do we have the will?

David R. Meldrum, M.D.,^a Marge A. Morris, M.Ed., R.D., C.D.E.,^b and Joseph C. Gambone, D.O., M.P.H.^c

^a Division of Reproductive Endocrinology and Infertility, Department of Reproductive Medicine, University of California, San Diego, California; ^b Diabetes Education and Nutrition Department, Mercy Regional Medical Center, Durango, Colorado; and ^c David Geffen School of Medicine, University of California, Los Angeles, California

Share of adults who are overweight or obese, 2022

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OBESITY

Energy expenditure

Energy intake

Adipose tissue

inflammation
insulin resistance

Liver

Metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) and steatohepatitis (MASH)

Bone

Osteoporosis

Skeletal muscle

sarcopenia

Addressing Obesity with the Ketogenic Diet

Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy Dovepress
open access to scientific and medical research

Open Access Full Text Article PERSPECTIVES

How Western Diet And Lifestyle Drive The Pandemic Of Obesity And Civilization Diseases

This article was published in the following Dove Press journal:
Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy

OPEN Western diet induces severe nonalcoholic steatohepatitis,

SCIENTIFIC REPORTS
nature research

Western Diet (WD)

Ketogenic Diet (KD)

- High fat
- Low CHO
- Adequate protein

Test whether **KD** is effective in mitigating WD-induced systemic inflammation and **hepatic** steatosis and if it might exert beneficial effects on **skeletal muscle** and **bone** tissues.

Addressing Obesity with the Ketogenic Diet

KD ameliorated hepatic steatosis WD-induced

Vegetal oil-based ketogenic diet improves inflammation and fibrosis in experimental metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis

Alessia Provera¹, Naresh Naik Ramavath¹, Laila Lavanya Gadipudi¹, Cristina Vecchio¹, Marina Caputo^{1,2}, Alessandro Antonioli¹, Sabrina Tini¹, Anteneh Nigussie Sheferaw¹, Simone Reano³, Nicoletta Filigheddu³, Marcello Manfredi³, Elettra Barberis⁴, Luca Coccolin⁵, Ilario Ferrocino⁵, Monica Locatelli⁶, Massimiliano Caprio^{7,8}, Frank Tacke⁹, Emanuele Albano¹, Flavia Prodám^{1,2†} and Salvatore Sutti^{1,4†}

Bone volume is reduced upon KD consumption

KD-dependent reduction of body, fat, and muscle weights

PLOS ONE

RESEARCH ARTICLE MUSCLE PERFORMANCES

Ketogenic diet preserves muscle mass and strength in a mouse model of type 2 diabetes

SCIENTIFIC REPORTS

OPEN

Ketogenic diet induces skeletal muscle atrophy via reducing muscle protein synthesis and possibly activating proteolysis in mice

SKELEAL MUSCLE

Reiko Nakao^{1,5}, Tomoki Abe^{1,5}, Saori Yamamoto¹ & Katsutaka Oishi^{1,2,3,4*}

KD-induced skeletal muscle atrophy

Unpublished results

KD activated KLF15-dependent protein degradation

BCAA levels

Short-term of KD feeding were sufficient in impacting muscle

Short-term of KD feeding were sufficient in impacting muscle

SD
WD
WD+KD

SD 18 weeks
WD 18 weeks
WD+KD 18 weeks

anti-laminin DAPI

Palmitate and butyrate dose-dependent atrophic effect

High dose of BU are detrimental for C2C12 myotubes

High dose of BU are detrimental for C2C12 myotubes

Low dose of BU mitigated PA-induced membrane depolarization

- PA500

BU50

Double-Edge Sword of KBs effects on skeletal muscle homeostasis **UPO**

-
- KD EFFECTS**
- Muscle mass
 - Myofiber size
 - BCAAs levels
- KLF15-dependent

-
- BU AT HIGH DOSE**
- Myotube width
 - Myosin expression
 - Mitochondrial membrane polarization

- BU AT LOW DOSE**
- Myotube width
 - Mitochondrial membrane polarization
 - Oxidative stress and inflammation

Double-Edge Sword of KBs effects on skeletal muscle homeostasis **UPO**

Flavia PRODAM
Nicoletta FILIGHEDDU

THANK YOU

...and to my team work

Tommaso RAITERI
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